

Building Community and a Creator Mindset Through Orff Schulwerk: Reflections from a Trip to Bali

ABSTRACT

The Balinese people and Orff practitioners share two core principles: community and creation. In this article, the author discusses how community emerges from the inseparability of music, movement, and drama, an integral part of each religious ceremony in Balinese communities and in Schulwerk classrooms. She compares the prominence of creation in Balinese life with the creative play that facilitates music learning within the Schulwerk.

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By Martina Vasil

The opportunity to go to Bali to study gamelan during my 2016 winter break came at an auspicious time. A series of life changes and the recent political climate had left me seeking escape and restoration and questioning the way we communicate with each other when opinions differ.

Although technology and the rise of social media have created opportunities for people to be more connected today than ever, people are instead becoming more isolated (Harris, 2015). There appear to be fewer opportunities to practice the interpersonal skills that develop when people interact. As Dunkelman (2014) observed, we tend to be connected to those on social media who hold worldviews similar to ours; their conversation threads demonstrate increasingly polarized views. Although it can be argued that social media platforms are “the new normal” for what it means to be part of a community, research shows that young adults (ages 19-32) who use social media feel more isolated than young adults who use it less frequently (Primack et al., 2017). This sense of isolation amidst technological connections is well illustrated in the music video *Are You Lost in the World Like Me?* by Moby and the Void Pacific Choir, with animation by Steve Cutts (2016).

Just as our sense of community is shifting, the spaces within which we create have changed as well. The accessibility of technology and social media has led to unprecedented opportunities for self-expression and, in particular, sharing these creations virtually with others online. Creating with others in the real world, however, particularly as part of a community effort, has become less a part of daily life (Rosen, 2015).

Shifts in community interactions and the spaces within which creation occurs have ramifications for music education. Although school music programs offer opportunities for students to create music together in the real world and interact with each other, it does not mean students are entirely comfortable with it. This discomfort was apparent recently as I presented dance workshops at a few local elementary schools. Many students avoided holding hands or even touching each other when doing dance movements, such as an elbow swing. When asked what they thought the hardest part of doing the dances was, the majority replied, "Dancing with each other." According to their teachers, their inability to communicate and work with one another is a common problem. As one shared with me, "They just can't work together, and it's getting worse."

Community and creation often came to mind during my time in Bali, where a palpable sense of community prevailed among the people in the village; music and the arts were woven throughout people's lives and brought them together. Villagers were actively engaged in all aspects of community and were expected to participate in ceremonies and musical performances. Creation was at the center of their lives—cooking, dancing, performing music, creating shadow puppets, and engaging in religious ceremonies.

Orff Schulwerk was also often on my mind, and not just because the Balinese gamelan had influenced Carl Orff's development of the barred instruments. Rather, I was struck by the similarities between the principles embodied by the Schulwerk and those of the Balinese people, particularly the core values of community and creation. Does the Orff Schulwerk classroom provide a sense of community and space for real-world creation and interaction that mirrors the lives of the Balinese people? What can music educators learn from the Balinese way of life?

A Historical Perspective: Balinese Gamelan and the Orff Instrumentarium

Although not the main focus here, it is important to explore briefly the connections between the Balinese gamelan and the Orff instrumentarium. Like other composers of the early 20th century, Orff was likely introduced to the sounds and style of gamelan music through the work of French composer Claude Debussy. Debussy had learned of the gamelan when he attended the Paris World Exhibition in 1889 (Parker, 2012). A Javanese gamelan orchestra performance inspired passages for several of Debussy's works, such as the piano composition *Pagodes* (Murray, 1978/2015; Parker, 2012).

The gamelan orchestra likely sounded unique to Debussy's ears for many reasons, for he was largely familiar with only Western European art music. First, gamelan is composed of mostly percussive sounds, including metal percussion—cymbals, single hanging gongs, tuned gongs suspended over resonator boxes, and double-sided drums. Second, the metal instruments of the gamelan orchestra are created slightly out of tune with each other to create a shimmering timbre when played at the same time. Third, each gamelan set is handmade for a community and the instruments are tuned to each other; the tuning of a gamelan from one village would not necessarily match the tuning of the instruments in a neighboring village (Parker, 2012).

The Balinese gamelan is similar to the Javanese gamelan Debussy experienced. Both include the *pemugal* (barred instruments), the *kendang* (drums), *reong* or *terompong* (bulb-shaped bells that are struck), gongs, the "turtle" (cymbals mounted on the back of a wooden sculpture of a turtle), singers, and sometimes *sulings* (bamboo flutes) and *rebabs* (string instruments) (de Panthou, 1978; Walton, 2007). Both Balinese and Javanese gamelan instruments carry certain "jobs"—some keep the pulse, others play the melody, and a few decorate or elaborate upon the melody. Balinese gamelan use only four pitches, roughly corresponding to "do," "re," "mi," and "sol" of the Western octave, whereas Javanese gamelan use five-pitch or seven-pitch scales (Brinner, 1995). Balinese gamelan are fabricated and owned by individual villages. Thus, the musical repertoire from one village to the next can vary widely (Tenzer, 1998).

Balinese and Javanese gamelan were not a direct inspiration for the metallophones in the Orff instrumentarium; Carl Orff did acknowledge, however, that specifically the wooden barred instruments from Indonesia were the source of some of his ideas (Orff, 1963). The primary influence of the barred instruments was the African xylophone (Calantropio & Frazee, 2008).

Balinese Culture

Bali is a small country nestled in the massive Indonesian archipelago in the South Asian Sea. Surrounded by thousands of islands with people who predominantly practice the Islamic faith, the dominant religious practice of Bali is “a true synthesis of Buddhism, Hinduism, and primitive animism” (de Panthou, 1978, p. 94). The religion is close to nature and includes the belief that spirits are present in all living and nonliving things (de Panthou, 1978; Ramstedt, 2004).

Considering the spirituality of the Balinese people, it is no surprise that gamelan music is used to enhance aesthetic and spiritual experiences. Typically, listeners are drawn into a meditative state by the repetitive, highly patterned, shimmering, penetrating sound (an experience very familiar to

those of us who work with the Orff instrumentarium). In their minds, they let go of the future and past and focus only on the present. As for the gamelan performers, it is expected they will experience both a physical and emotional connection to their personal truth, a phenomenon referred to as *rasa* (Walton, 2007).

The ritual invocation of the spirit is part of all activity in Bali, not just musical practices. Every morning in my short time on the island, my host family made offerings of flowers, palm leaves, and rice to the gods (see Figure 1). Every family has a temple in their home or on their grounds to use for various purposes (see Figure 2). During my visit, one family used their temple to celebrate a child’s birthday. The grandfather chanted, blessed the food for a long time, and placed offerings to the gods before the child.

Community temples throughout the island are used for various purposes such as blessing the construction of a new building. At one of these ceremonies I attended, all those present were invited to participate in the prayer, during which priests came to every seated person to pour a little bit of holy water into his or her hands and press a few pieces of rice to his or her forehead (see Figure 3,

Figure 1: An Offering by the Water.

Figure 2: A Family Temple.

Figure 3: Rice Remains on the Foreheads of Sarah Greer and Martina Vasil after the Ceremony.

SOURCE: PHOTOS BY MARTINA VASIL. USED WITH PERMISSION.

p. 38). Both family and community ceremonies are so pervasive that the smell of incense is everywhere.

Through the ubiquitous presence of ceremony in daily life, the sacred is made ordinary, and the ordinary is made sacred. According to de Panthou (1978), the purpose of these rituals is “to please the souls of the ancestors. A little food has only to be placed on the earth to drive away evil spirits” (p. 102). A practical consequence exists as well—building community through reinforcement of social and cultural bonds.

Balinese Culture and Orff Schulwerk

In Bali, there was a sense of community and space for real-world creation and interaction similar to that in my Orff Schulwerk classroom and in the classrooms of colleagues who follow the Orff approach. A large part of this community connection comes from the inseparability of music, movement, and drama, which are an integral part of each religious ceremony in Balinese communities and an integral part of the Orff approach. Orff called this phenomenon “elemental music.”

What, then, is elemental music? Never music alone, but music connected with movement, dance, and speech—not to be listened to, meaningful only in active participation. Elemental music is pre-intellectual, it lacks great form, it contents itself with simple sequential structures, ostinatos [*sic*], and miniature rondos. It is earthy, natural, almost a physical activity. It can be learned and enjoyed by anyone. (1963, p. 72)

Orff’s definition of elemental music, particularly the emphasis on the interconnectedness of movement, dance, and speech and the notion of its being available to all, could well be describing ceremonial practices of the Balinese people. Gamelan music, movement, and drama accompany all rituals and ceremonies, and everybody in the community is involved in some way.

For example, while I was teaching a Balinese dance routine, children as young as 5 years old came to the family compound to participate. They were already mastering the curved toes, graceful arms, and darting eyes that make Balinese dance so distinctive. Other family members joined in on the gamelan to provide the music. This lovely, spontaneously unfolding movement and music-making

Figure 4: The Author Copies the Movements of the Balinese Dance Teacher.

PHOTOGRAPHER: CECILIA WANG. USED WITH PERMISSION.

exercise evoked a vision of a similar scene in an Orff classroom, where the emphasis is on full participation and playful exploration, and the goal is as much about the experience of the musicians and their connection to one another as it is about the presentation. The musicians support the dancers, just as the dancers support the musicians (see Figure 4).

Creation is central to Balinese life, because artistry is understood as being an integral part of every person’s humanity. From the time a child is born, he or she is immersed in artistic practices: theatre, dance, music, painting, and sculpture. As de Panthou (1978) explains:

The Balinese consider art a natural activity belonging to everyday life, and not as an end in

itself. Artistic expression, closely connected to religious ritual, is considered above all an act of faith to satisfy the gods during their stay here on earth. It is thus no exaggeration to say that on the island, there are as many artists as there are inhabitants. (p. 72)

Orff placed great value on creation and believed every child was musical. He thought music education should bring out the natural spontaneity and musicality of children (1963). Thus, in the Schulwerk, music learning is active, collaborative, and occurs through creative play (Huffman, 2012; Shehan, 1985).

Conclusion

What can music educators learn from the Balinese way of life? The importance of community and creation permeates all aspects of Balinese culture. We as Orff Schulwerk teachers are familiar with the magic that occurs when children are working together to bring music they have created to life. We know the deep connections made when music is situated within a cultural context and enhanced

through speech, movement, and drama. Further, the feeling experienced when performing music with others as well as hearing the sonorous qualities of the instruments in an Orff classroom may come very close to the Balinese state of *rasa*. We may consider the Orff classroom similar to a Balinese temple—a sanctuary devoted to ritual, where simple but soulful connections are made and all are welcome to join in. In this context it is possible to think of Orff Schulwerk as a spiritual practice, not in a religious sense, but perhaps as a celebration of individual creativity and of our sacred obligation to one another.

Given these parallels, I believe Orff Schulwerk teachers in the United States could benefit from learning more about gamelan music and Balinese culture, whether through participating in a gamelan ensemble in their community or at a local higher education institution or, if possible, by visiting Bali. My trip had a profound impact on me as an educator and a human being. To see people blend music, movement, and drama into so many aspects of their lives and openly invite all to participate in the music making was truly an inspiration. ■

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